

Finding Attackers Details to Solve Security Issues Using Honeypots Technique

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 6

Special Issue : 1

Month : September

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Thanigasalam, S ;
Savitha Devi, M.
(2018). Finding
Attackers Details to
Solve Security Issues
Using Honeypots
Technique. *Shanlax
International Journal
of Arts, Science and
Humanities*, 6(S1),
pp.72–75

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.1410987](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1410987)

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Abstract

In the real-world network system, an enormous number of applications and services available for data transmission. The data may access from one place to another place is also possible today. In wireless data transmission, some of the problems may arise like loss of a data; data destination missing and some network related issues are also mainly intruders, hackers, virus, and worms. The already available techniques may find the attack, but there is no aware about which the third party may access the data. In that, a new process called honeypots is used to search the attacker details. With the help of this technique, the attacker may easily identify and easily blocked by the user. In this paper, we will discuss how honeypots are used for security purpose and its involvement in various fields effectively to solve security issues.

Introduction

There are many types of computer networks are local-area networks (LANs), Wide-area networks (WANs), Metropolitan-area networks (MANs). Network security consists of the policies and practices adopted to prevent and monitor unauthorized access, misuse, modification, or denial of a computer network and network-accessible resources. Network security involves the authorization of access to data in a network, which is controlled by the network administrator.

Network security starts with Authentication, commonly with a username and a password. Since this requires just one detail authenticating the user name—i.e., the password—this is sometimes termed one-factor authentication. With two-factor authentication, something the user 'has' is also used (e.g., a security token or 'dongle,' an ATM card, or a mobile phone); and with three-factor authentication, something the user 'is' is also used (e.g., a fingerprint or retinal scan).

Once authenticated, a firewall enforces access policies such as what services are allowed to be accessed by the network users. Though effective to prevent unauthorized access, this component

may fail to check potentially harmful content such as computer worms or Trojans being transmitted over the network. Honeypots essentially decoy network-accessible resources, may be deployed in a network as surveillance and early-warning tools, as the honeypots are not naturally accessed for legitimate purposes. Techniques used by the attackers that attempt to compromise these decoy resources are studied during and after an attack to keep an eye on new exploitation techniques. Such analysis may be used to further tighten the security of the actual network being protected by the honeypot. A honeypot can also direct an attacker's attention away from legitimate servers.

Honeypots

In computer terminology, a honey pot is a trap set to detect, deflect, or, in some manner, counteract attempts at unauthorized use of information systems. Generally, a honey pot consists of a computer, data, or a network site that appears to be part of a network, but is isolated and monitored, and which seems to contain information or a resource of value to attackers. This is similar to the police baiting a criminal and then conducting undercover surveillance.

Types of Honeypots

Honeypots can be classified based on their deployment (use/action) and based on their level of involvement. Based on the advantage, honeypots may be classified as

- production honeypots
- research honeypots

Production Honeypots

It is easy to cash, capture only limited information, and are used primarily by corporations. Production honeypots are placed inside the production network with other production servers by an organization to improve their overall state of security. Normally, production honeypots are low-interaction honeypots, which are easier to deploy. They give less information about the attacks or attackers than research honeypots.

Research Honeypots

It runs to gather information about the motives and tactics of the black hat community targeting different networks. These honeypots do not add direct value to a specific organization; instead, they are used to research the threats that organizations face and to learn how to better protect against those threats. Research honeypots are complex to deploy and maintain, capture extensive information and are used primarily by research, military, or government organizations.

Based on design criteria, honeypots can be classified as:

- pure honeypots
- high-interaction honeypots
- low-interaction honeypots

Pure honeypots are full-fledged production systems. No other software needs to be installed. Even though a pure honey pot is useful, stealthiest of the defense mechanisms can be ensured by a more controlled system.

High-interaction honeypots imitate the activities of the production systems that host a variety of services and, therefore, an attacker may be allowed a lot of services to waste his time. By employing virtual machines, multiple honeypots can be hosted on a single physical device. Therefore, even if the honey pot is compromised, it can be restored more quickly. In general, high-interaction honeypots provide more security by being difficult to detect, but they are expensive to maintain. If virtual machines are not available, one physical computer must be protecting for each honey pot,

which can be exorbitantly expensive. Example: Honey net. Low-interaction honeypots simulate only the services frequently requested by attackers. Since they consume relatively few resources, multiple virtual machines can easily be hosted on one physical system, the virtual method have a short response time, and less code is required, reducing the complexity of the virtual system's security. Example: Honeyd.

Honeypots Technology

Malware Honeypots

Malware honeypots are used to detect malware by exploiting the known replication and attack vectors of malware. Replication vectors such as USB flash drives can easily be verified for evidence of modifications, either through manual means or utilizing special-purpose honeypots that emulate drives.

Spam Versions

Spammers abuse vulnerable resources such as open mail relays and open proxies. Some system administrators have created honey pot programs that masquerade as these abusable resources to discover spammer activity. There are several capabilities such honeypots provide to these administrators, and the existence of such fake abusable systems makes abuse more difficult or risky. Honeypots can be a powerful countermeasure to misuse from those who rely on very high volume abuse (e.g., spammers).

These honeypots can reveal the abuser's IP address and provide bulk spam capture (which enables operators to determine spammers' URLs and response mechanisms). For open relay honeypots, it is possible to determine the e-mail addresses ("drop boxes") spammers' use as targets for their test messages, which are the tool they use to detect open relays. It is then simple to deceive the spammer: transmit any illicit relay e-mail received addressed to that drop box e-mail address. That tells the spammer the honey pot is a genuine abusable open relay, and they often respond by sending large quantities of relay spam to that honey pot, which stops it. The apparent source may be another abused system—spammers and other abusers may use a chain of abused systems to make detection of the original starting point of the abuse traffic difficult.

This in itself is indicative of the power of honeypots as anti-spam tools. In the early days of anti-spam honeypots, spammers, with little concern for hiding their location, felt safe testing for vulnerabilities and sending spam directly from their systems. Honeypots made the abuse riskier and more difficult.

Spam still flows through open relays, but the volume is much smaller than in 2001 to 2002. While most spam originates in the U.S. spammers hop through open relays across political boundaries to mask their origin. Honey pot operators may use intercepted relay tests to recognize and thwart attempts to relay spam through their honeypots. "Thwart" may mean "accept the relay spam but decline to deliver it." Honey pot operators may discover other details concerning the spam and the spammer by examining the captured spam messages.

Email Trap

An email address that is used for any other purpose than to receive spam can also be considered a spam honey pot. Compared with the term "spam trap," the term "honey pot" might be more suitable for systems and techniques that are used to detect or counterattacks and probes. With a spam trap, spam arrives at its destination "legitimately"—exactly as non-spam email would arrive.

Database Honeypot

Databases often get attacked by intruders using SQL Injection. As such activities are not recognized by basic firewalls, companies often use database firewalls for protection. Some of the available SQL database firewalls provide/support honey pot architectures so that the intruder runs against a trap database while the web application remains functional.

Honey Nets

Two or more honeypots on a network form a honey net. Typically, a honey net is used for monitoring a larger and more diverse network in which one honeypot may not be sufficient. Honey nets and honeypots are usually implemented as parts of larger network intrusion detection systems.

Conclusion

Network security can handle different attack day by day. This paper discusses such attacks measures by possibly tracing the attacker and its mode of attack. Honeypots are a key tool to identify the hacker's attacks. Honeypots are used to collect the information about the hackers and also alert the network administrator of a possible intrusion by trailing the attacker. Honeypots are used a lot of security purpose such as email trap, spam, malware to increase efficiency.

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